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COVER ART – Illustration by Jason Poole of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Drexel University. A juvenile or diminutive species of hadrosaurid dinosaur is scavenged by multiple sharks in a shallow, near-shore marine setting.

FIRST RECORD OF THE SYNECHODONTIFORM SHARK *SPHENODUS* (NEOSELACHII, ORTHACODONTIDAE) FROM THE DANIAN OF EASTERN NORTH AMERICA

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ABSTRACT - The rare, cold-water synechodontiform shark *Sphenodus* is here reported from the Hornerstown Formation (Danian) of Gloucester County, New Jersey. A well-preserved, upper-right lateral tooth was recovered from the Inversand Company glauconite quarry in June 2011. Based on size, tooth crown and root morphology, and age, the tooth (NJSM GP23223) is assigned to *Sphenodus lundgreni* (Davis, 1890) and represents the first record of this taxon from the Danian of eastern North America.

INTRODUCTION

The Hungerford and Terry (Inversand) glauconite quarry in Gloucester County, New Jersey (**Fig. 1**), has long been a source of latest Cretaceous (Maastrichtian) and earliest Paleocene (Danian) fossils. During a joint field expedition (**Fig. 2**) between the New Jersey State Museum, Drexel University, and the Delaware Valley Paleontological Society, in early June 2011, a well-preserved, lateral shark tooth of unusual morphology was recovered. The tooth (NJSM GP23223) was found alongside the main excavations, following the removal of overburden from the Main Fossiliferous Layer of MFL (**Fig. 3**), which has produced numerous vertebrate fossils. The tooth was identified, via email on June 10, 2011, by David Ward of Orpington, England as the upper-right lateral tooth of the Synechodontiform shark *Sphenodus lundgreni*. This is the first record of this species from the Americas and the lowest latitudinal occurrence in the Northern Hemisphere.

Figure 1. Map of New Jersey. The black star indicates the approximate location of the Inversand Quarry.

Figure 2. Workers expose the Main Fossiliferous Layer of the Hornerstown Formation during the 2011 field study. The *Sphenodus* tooth (NJSM GP23223) was uncovered from a gully alongside the main work area.

GEOLOGIC SETTING

The Hungerford and Terry Inc. (Inversand) quarry is the last remnant of the greensand marl mining industry that thrived in southern New Jersey beginning in the late 1700's (Weishampel and Young, 1996).

The quarry, which will be referred to here as "Inversand," lies within New Jersey's inner coastal plain, which preserves marine sediments deposited during latest Cretaceous and early to mid-Paleogene time. The stratigraphic section at Inversand, especially the New Egypt and Hornerstown formations, has been described and discussed in detail by Gallagher (1993, 2002, 2003), Staron et al. (2001), Parris and Hope (2002), Landman et al. (2004b), Landman et al. (2007) and Obasi et al. (2011) among others. Here we give a brief

summary of the geologic section at the site (Fig. 3).

The lowest part of the quarry at Inversand consists of approximately 3.2 meters of massive, unconsolidated glauconitic sand which has been variously assigned to the Navesink Formation by some authors (Gallagher, 1993; Staron et al., 2001; Obasi et al., 2011), and to the New Egypt Formation by others (Landman et al., 2004b; Landman et al., 2007). Here we refer it to the New Egypt Formation, based on the findings of Landman et al. (2004b) and faunal similarities to a recently discovered New Egypt Formation vertebrate fauna in southern Monmouth County (Callahan et al., 2010). The New Egypt Formation conformably overlies the Navesink Formation.

Figure 3. Stratigraphic section at the Inversand quarry. NJSMP GP23223 most likely came from either the MFL or the Middle Fossil Assemblage. (after Gallagher 2003).

Disconformably overlying the New Egypt Formation at the Inversand site is the Hornerstown Formation, which has a thickness of approximately 5.5 meters. The Hornerstown Formation at Inversand is a moderately sorted, medium to fine grained, almost pure glauconitic sand. The basal disconformity is not easily observed in outcrop due to extensive bioturbation (Ralph Johnson pers comm., 2013), and the formation as a whole is heavily burrowed.

Within the basal part of the Hornerstown Formation lies the Main Fossiliferous Layer, or MFL. The MFL has been a source of numerous invertebrate and vertebrate fossils for over 70 years and has produced fossils from latest Cretaceous (Maastrichtian) to early Paleogene (Danian) age. The MFL averages approximately 0.3 meters in thickness. Several meters above the MFL is an additional fossiliferous layer, which has a much lower faunal diversity than the MFL, and appears to represent a rebound fauna following the end-Cretaceous extinction event.

The Hornerstown Formation is overlain by approximately 3 meters of the Paleocene (Selandian) Vincentown Formation, which is, in turn, capped by the Kirkwood (Miocene) and Cohansey (?Pliocene) formations.

Since NJSM GP23223 was not found in-situ, the exact stratigraphic position of the tooth cannot be certain. When found, the tooth had typical Hornerstown glauconitic greensand adhering to its base. This, and the fact that the tooth was discovered immediately following the removal of overburden from the MFL, strongly suggests that the tooth originated from either the MFL or the “upper fossiliferous layer” of the Hornerstown Formation.

Institutional Abbreviations

MGUH, Geological Museum, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark; **NJSM**, New Jersey State Museum, Trenton, New Jersey, USA; **WAM**, Western Australian Museum, Welshpool, Western Australia, Australia.

SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

Class CHONDRICHTHYES Huxley, 1880
 Subclass ELASMOBRANCHI Bonaparte, 1838
 Subcohort NEOSELACHII Compagno, 1977
 Superorder SQUALMOMORPHII
 Compagno 1973
 Order SYNECHODONTIFORMES,
 Duffin & Ward, 1993
 Family ORTHACODONTIDAE Glikman, 1957
 Genus *SPHENODUS* Agassiz, 1843

SPHENODUS LUNDGRENI (Davis, 1890)

Referred Material—NJSM GP23223, a single complete upper-right lateral tooth (**Fig. 4**).

Locality and Horizon—Hungerford and Terry Inversand Quarry, Sewell, Mantua Township, Gloucester County, New Jersey, USA; Hornerstown Formation, early Danian.

Description—NJSM GP23223 is a complete, very well preserved, upper-right, lateral tooth measuring 34 mm in overall height and with a root length of 14 mm. The crown height is 26 mm along the anterior edge and 24 mm along the posterior edge. NJSM GP23223 is assigned to *Sphenodus lundgreni* based on the following characteristics:

- Tearing-type crown lingually inclined and moderately sigmoidal in lateral view.

- Salient anterior and posterior cutting edges flanked by blade-like enameloid ridges that extend as heels along the upper surfaces of the root and bear numerous vertical folds which continue onto the base, especially on the lingual side.
- Base of crown bearing short vertical folds on the labial side and fine ridges just above the root on the lingual side: upper labial and lingual crown faces smooth.
- Root sub-oval in outline with a prominent lingual extension and a flattened, slightly convex basal surface.
- Pseudopolyaulacorhize root with shallow labiolingual horizontal vascular canals on the basal face and numerous, small vascular foramina over the entire surface of the root.

Figure 4. *Sphenodus lundgreni* (NJSM GP23223). A, labial view. B, posterior view. C, occlusal view. D, lingual view. E, basal view.

DISCUSSION

Davis (1890) originally described teeth of *S. lundgreni* from material recovered from the Danian of Sweden and Denmark. He named the species *Oxyrhina lundgreni* but not without hesitation due to the “flat under-surface of the root” (page 395). He did not assign any of his figured specimens as the type specimen, so all of them must be considered syntypes. Davis (1890) notes (page 394) that “the root is not well preserved on any of the Swedish examples” and only one of his figured

specimens shows a full root. That specimen (Davis, 1890, plate XXXIX, fig 9) now resides in the Geological Museum of the University of Copenhagen, Denmark as MGUH 1406 (**Fig. 5** is Davis’ original illustration and **Fig. 6** is a photograph of the specimen as it appears today). This well-preserved antero-lateral tooth is currently under consideration for assignment as lectotype of *S. lundgreni* (Giles Cuny and Jan Adolfssen, pers. comm., August 2012).

Figure 5. Illustration from Davis (1890). His figures 8 through 11 represent syntypes of *Sphenodus lundgreni* Figure 9 is the proposed lectotype.

Figure 6. *Sphenodus lundgreni* (MGUH 1406). This is the specimen illustrated by Davis (1890, figure 9). It is the current candidate for being designated as the species lectotype.

WAM 11.12.1 (fig. 7) shows an anterior tooth of *S. lundgreni* from the type area that was on loan to the NJSM courtesy of Mikael Siverson. It illustrates the much higher crown height of the anterior teeth and the very large size that *S. lundgreni* could attain. It has been suggested by Siverson (1995) that the extinction of large meat cutting sharks like *Squalicorax* at the end of the Cretaceous may have opened mid-shelf areas of the northern latitudes to more primitive sharks such as *Sphenodus*.

The genus *Sphenodus* has a temporal range that extends from Early Jurassic into the early Paleogene (Duffin and Ward, 1993). The only other report of the genus in North America is of specimens referred to, in a non-technical shark tooth guide, as *Sphenodus* sp., from the Upper Cretaceous of Hornby Island,

British Columbia, Canada (Hessin et al., 2007). The Paleogene record is limited to a single species, *Sphenodus lundgreni*, a large shark previously known only from the Danian of Scandinavia (Davis, 1890; Cappetta, 1987), Russia (Evgeny Popov, pers. comm., February, 2012), and Kazakhstan (David Ward, pers. comm., June, 2011). Additional specimens of *S. cf. lundgreni* have been reported by Bendix-Almgreen (1969) from Greenland and by Mannering and Hiller (2008) from New Zealand. Other post-Jurassic occurrences of *Sphenodus* sp. are known from the Lower Cretaceous of France and Poland and the Upper Cretaceous of Japan and Switzerland (Cappetta, 1987) and Antarctica (Kriwet et al., 2006). It has also been recovered from the Maastrichtian of Angola (Atunes and Cappetta, 2002).

Figure 7. Large anterior tooth of *Sphenodus lundgreni* (WAM 11.12.1) from the Danian of Limhamn Quarry, Malmö, Sweden the type area for the taxon. A, lingual view. B, lateral view. C, basal view.

NOTE ON RANGE AND CLASSIFICATION OF SYNECHODONTIFORMES

The Synechodontiformes have an extremely long temporal range. Ivanov (2005) describes *Synechodus antiquus*, based on several teeth, from the Early Permian, Artinskian marine limestone/marl in the Russian Federation. Cappetta (2012: page 321) lists the range of the type genus, *Synechodus*, as “Lower Triassic, Scythian-lower Paleocene, Danian; Europe, Russia, North America.” *Paraorthacodus* includes numerous species ranging from Middle Jurassic; Aalenian to Paleocene: Thanetian (Duffin and Ward,

1993). *Sphenodus* dates from the Early Jurassic.

The classification of genera within Synechodontiformes has been a matter of controversy. Cappetta (1986 and 2012) assigns *Sphenodus* to Hexanchoidae. Duffin and Ward (1993) erected the order Synechodontiformes and include within it the families: Orthacodontidae, with a single genus *Sphenodus*, and Paleospinachidae, which includes *Synechodus* and *Paraorthacodus*. Duffin and Ward (2003) considered Synechodontiformes to be the sister-group to hexanchids.

Underwood and Ward (2004a) erected the family Pseudonotidanidae within Synechodontiformes, with two genera: *Welcommia* and *Pseudonotidanus*.

Maisey et al. (2004: page 40) consider the various genera assigned to the Synechodontiformes to be “an assortment of several extinct stem representatives of various neoselachian and/or galeomorph lineages.” Klug (2010), utilizing phylogenetic analysis with robust cladistic principles, concludes that Synechodontiformes is a monophyletic clade and is sister group to all living sharks. Based on her findings, Klug (2010) divides the Synechodontiformes into four families: Pseudonotidanidae (*Welcommia*, *Pseudonotidanus*), Orthacodontidae (*Sphenodus*), Paleospinachidae (*Palidiplospinax*, *Synechodus*) and a new family: Paraorthacodontidae (*Paraorthacodus*, *Macrourgaleus*). For now, we follow the classification of Klug (2010). It is of interest to note that the Synechodontiformes (sensu Klug, 2010) is the “only group of neoselachian sharks which is considered to cross the Jurassic/Triassic boundary” (Klug, 2010, page 38).

FUTURE INVESTIGATION

As a caveat for further investigation it must be noted that the roots of synechodontiform sharks are seldom preserved and it is possible that isolated tooth crowns of *S. lundgreni* have been recovered in other North American Danian localities but mis-identified as lamniform teeth, which they closely resemble. We encourage scrutiny of Danian chondrichthyan tooth collections from Atlantic and Gulf Coastal Plain localities for other possible occurrences of this rare taxon.

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LITERATURE CITED

- Agassiz, L. 1843. *Recherches Sur Les Poissons Fossiles*. Tome III (livr. 18). Imprimerie de Petitpierre, Neuchatel. 390 pp., 32 pl.
- Antunes, M. T. and H. Cappetta. 2002. Sélachiens du Crétacé (Albian-Maastrichtian) d' Angola. *Palaeontographica A*, 264:85-146.
- Bendix-Almgreen, S. E. 1969. Notes on the Upper Cretaceous and Lower Tertiary fish faunas of northern West Greenland. *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 19:204-217.
- Bonaparte, C.L. 1838. *Selachorum tabula analytica*. *Nuovi Annali della Science Naturali Bologna*, 1 (2): 195-214.
- Callahan, W. R., R. O. Johnson and C. M. Mehling. 2010. A new vertebrate assemblage from the Late Cretaceous (Maastrichtian) New Egypt Formation of New Jersey. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology, Program and Abstracts*, 2010, 68A.
- Cappetta, H. 1987. Chondrichthyes II: Mesozoic and Cenozoic Elasmobranchii. *Handbook of Paleichthyology*, Volume 3B. Gustav Fischer Verlag, Stuttgart, 193 pp.
- Cappetta, H., 2012. Chondrichthyes: Mesozoic and Cenozoic Elasmobranchii: teeth. *Handbook of Paleichthyology*, Volume 3E. Gustav Fischer Verlag, Stuttgart, 512 pp.
- Compagno, L.J.V. 1973. Interrelationships of living elasmobranchs. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 53 (Supplement 1): 15-61.
- Compagno, L.J.V. 1977. Phyletic relationships of living sharks and rays. *American Zoologist*, 17 (2): 303-322.
- Davis, J. W. 1890. On the fossil fish of the Cretaceous formations of Scandinavia. *Scientific Transactions of the Royal Dublin Society*, (2), 4(6):363-434.
- Duffin, C. J., and D. J. Ward. 1993. The Early Jurassic palaeospinacid sharks of Lyme Regis, southern England. *Belgian Geological Survey, Professional Paper* 264:53-102.
- Gallagher, W. B. 1993. The Cretaceous/Tertiary mass extinction event in the northern Atlantic Coastal Plain. *The Mosasaur* 5: 75-154.
- Gallagher, W. B., 2002. Faunal changes across the Cretaceous-Tertiary (K-T) boundary in the Atlantic Coastal Plain of New Jersey: Restructuring the marine community after the K-T mass-extinction event. *In* Koebel, C. and K. G. MacLeod, eds., *Catastrophic events and mass extinctions: impacts and beyond: Boulder, Colorado, Geological Society of America Special Paper* 356: 291-301.

- Gallagher, W. B., 2003. Oligotrophic oceans and minimalist organisms: collapse of the Maastrichtian marine ecosystem and Paleocene recovery in the Cretaceous-Tertiary sequence of New Jersey. *Netherlands Journal of Geosciences / Geologie en Mijnbouw*, 82(3): 225-231.
- Hessin, W. A., K. Mortison and D. Bowen 2007. Pictorial guide to the fossil shark teeth from the Upper Cretaceous of Hornby Island, British Columbia, Canada. Digital Production, William A. Hessin. 8 pp.
- Huxley, T. H. 1880. On the application of the laws of evolution to the arrangement of the Vertebrata, and more particularly of the Mammalia. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society, London*, 43:649-662.
- Ivanov, A. 2005. Early Permian chondrichthyans of the Middle and South Urals. *Revista Brasileira de Paleontologia* 8(2):127-138.
- Klug, S. 2010. Monophyly, phylogeny and systematic position of the Synechodontiformes (Chondrichthyes, Neoselachii). *Zoologica Scripta*, 39(1):37-49.
- Kriwet, J., J. M. Lirio, H. J. Nuñez, E. Puecat, and C. Lécuyer. 2006. Late Cretaceous Antarctic fish diversity. In Francis, J. E., D. Pirrie., and J. A. Crame. (eds), *Cretaceous-Tertiary High-Latitude Palaeoenvironments, James Ross Basin, Antarctica*. Geological Society, London Special Publications, 258:83-100.
- Landman, N. H., R. O. Johnson and L. E. Edwards. 2004b. Cephalopods from the Cretaceous/Tertiary boundary interval on the Atlantic Coastal Plain, with a description of the highest ammonite zones in North America. Part 2. Northeastern Monmouth County, New Jersey. *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History*, 287: 107 pp.
- Landman, N. H., R. O. Johnson, M. P. Garb, L. E. Edwards and F. T. Kyte. 2007. Cephalopods from the Cretaceous/Tertiary boundary interval on the Atlantic Coastal Plain, with a description of the highest ammonite zones in North America. Part 3. Manasquan River Basin, Monmouth County, New Jersey. *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History*, 303: 122 pp.
- Maisey, J. G., G. J. P. Naylor and D. J. Ward. 2004. Mesozoic elasmobranchs, neoselachian phylogeny and the rise of modern elasmobranch diversity. *Mesozoic Fishes 3 - Systematics, Palaeoenvironments and Biodiversity*. In: Arratia G. and A. Tinori, eds. *Mesozoic fishes 3 – systematics, palaeoenvironments and biodiversity*. Munich: Dr. Friedrich Pfeil, 17-56.
- Mannering, A.A., and N. Hiller. 2008. An early Cenozoic neoselachian shark fauna from the Southwest Pacific. *Palaeontology* 51(6): 1341-1365.
- Obasi, C. C., D. O. Terry, G. H. Myer and D. E. Grandstaff. 2011. Glauconite composition and morphology, shocked quartz, and the origin of the Cretaceous (?) Main Fossiliferous Layer (MFL) in southern New Jersey, U.S.A. *Journal of Sedimentary Research*, 81: 479-494.

- Parris, D. C. and S. Hope. 2002. New Interpretations of the Birds from the Navesink and Hornerstown Formations, New Jersey, USA (Aves: Neornithies). *In* Zhou, Z. and F. Zhang, eds., 2002. Proceedings of the 5th Symposium of the Society of Avian Paleontology and Evolution, Beijing, 1-4 June 2000. Science Press, Beijing, China: 113-120.
- Siverson, M. 1995. Revision of the Danian cow sharks, sand tiger sharks, and goblin sharks (Hexanchidae, Odontaspidae, and Mijsukuridae) from southern Sweden. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 15(1): 1-12.
- Staron, R. M., B. S. Grandstaff, W. B. Gallagher and D. E. Grandstaff. 2001. REE signatures in vertebrate fossils from Sewell, NJ: Implications for location of the K-T Boundary. *Palaios*, 16: 255-265.
- Underwood, C. J. and D. J. Ward. 2004a. Neoselachian sharks and rays from the British Bathonian (Middle Jurassic). *Palaentology*, 47, 447-501
- Weishampel, D. B., and L. Young. 1996. *Dinosaurs of the East Coast*. The Johns Hopkins University Press, 275 pp.